

**ROMANIAN ASSOCIATION OF YOUNG SCHOLARS
(RAYS)**

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(Editors)

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BOOK OF ABSTRACTS

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Dear Colleagues,

The Romanian Association of Young Scholars (RAYS) is delighted to welcome you to the first edition of our International Interdisciplinary Doctoral Conference (IIDC 2015). The event takes place on the 25th – 26th of September 2015 at the RIN Grand Hotel Conference Center, on no. 7D Vitan-Barzesti Highway, Bucharest.

On this occasion, we brought together contributions from doctoral students, researchers and faculty staff within the fields of political science, international relations, history, law, sociology, philosophy, educational studies, cultural and literary studies, and economics on the themes listed in our Call for Papers.

The Romanian Association of Young Scholars wants to thank the Ministry of Education for the support, openness and promptitude with which it has answered to our event. We also want to express our gratitude to the co-organizers of this event – the Faculty of Political Science of the National School of Political Science and Public Administration, the Department of International Relations and European Integration of the National School of Political Science and Public Administration, the European Institute of Romania, the Institute for Educational Sciences, the Center for Research in Applied Ethics of the Faculty of Philosophy of the University of Bucharest, the Doctoral School of Letters of the University of Bucharest, the Research Institute for the Quality of Life of the Romanian Academy, the “Nicolae Iorga” Institute for History of the Romanian Academy, the Center of Studies and Research “Society, Law, Religion” – and also to the media partner of the conference, Observatorul Cultural.

We thank you for joining us!
The Organizing Team

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National School of Political Science and Public Administration

**Department of International Relations and
European Integration,**
National School of Political Science and Public Administration

Center for Research in Applied Ethics,
Faculty of Philosophy, University of Bucharest

European Institute of Romania

Research Institute for Quality of Life,
Romanian Academy

Doctoral School of Letters,
University of Bucharest

Institute for Educational Sciences

“Nicolae Iorga” Institute for History,
Romanian Academy

Center of Studies and Research “Society, Law, Religion”

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**IT IS NOT THAT FUNNY. OLD RACIST IDEAS AND BELIEFS IN
THE NEW ERA OF SOCIAL MEDIA: A CRITICAL ANALYSIS**

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Brazilian society has changed and improved significantly within the past four decades in comparison to previous periods on what concerns many socio-economic indicators. Within that, it is also possible to notice that presently, many Black individuals play a larger array of relevant social roles than their previous generations. Nevertheless, they are still subject of persistent negative stigmas, stereotypes and are portrayed on limited social roles by the country's dominant elite, or they are considered as the sugar at the bottom of the cup of tea as Stuart Hall used to describe such picture. Given that discourse is also a mechanism to manifest power relations between social groups, it can be observed that disparagement humour plays an important role on the production and reinforcement of their symbolical social displacement. Jokes are considered socially acceptable form of communication, and on top of that, capable to convey in a metaphorical way what would not usually be openly said on a regular face-to-face interaction due to social convention constraints. Indeed, they act as a convenient vehicle to conceal racist discourses. Therefore, given this broad scenario, this research aims at investigating old racist ideas and beliefs concealed in derogatory jokes freely displayed on social media. For this purpose, the research will make use of Critical Discourse Analysis to evaluate comments made by Facebook users in communities displaying such content, and also analyse the narratives and discussions of Black adult individuals taking part on focus groups and in-depth interviews about their perspective on this subject matter. The expectation is that this research will contribute to fill a gap in the literature regarding the analysis of racist discourses under the perspective of humorous discourses and also to better comprehend the complexity behind the discrepancy between the current social roles of those individuals and those who are persistently attributed to them.

Keywords: *disparagement humour; social media, racism; prejudice; black individuals.*